

THE PROBLEM OF NORMATIVITY IN EXPLANATORY ENGLISH DICTIONARIES

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Annotation:

Knowledge of dictionaries and reference books, the culture of using them is an integral part of the training of a wide range of specialists . Today, a large number of the most diverse dictionaries are published both by type, and by volume, and by purpose. The thesis deals with the most widespread problems in dictionaries of the modern English language.

Key words:

Spelling problems, lexicography, explanatory dictionary, etymological dictionary, orthoepic dictionaries, phraseological units.

Introduction

There is no argument that the translator faces difficulties in translating some words, collocations .The problems in explanatory dictionaries continue the tradition of "dictionaries of irregularities" that developed in English lexicography as early as the 19th - early 20th centuries. Correctness dictionaries (orthological dictionaries - from orthology is a section of linguistics, the object of which is the theory of correct literary speech; Greek orthos - correct and logos - word, concept, doctrine) - these are dictionaries of a normative-stylistic nature, by genre they belong to dictionaries dedicated to problems codification and normalization of the literary language. Dictionaries of this type answer the question of how best, how to say which option to prefer in a given speech situation. - normative dictionaries that serve to improve the language and speech, strengthen the current norms of the literary language.

Today, a large number of the most diverse dictionaries are published both in type, volume, and purpose, but they do not always meet modern lexicographic requirements and trends of the times. Consider the most popular unconditionally interesting dictionaries of the English language. These are, first of all, normative dictionaries, which include spelling, explanatory and correct speech dictionaries¹

¹А.Влагова "Новейшие нормативные словари русского языка"

Spelling problems concern absolutely everyone who deals with written speech. Although spelling has existed for centuries without much change, nevertheless, the level of education and the actual complexity of the spelling rules of the English language, as well as a significant number of so-called dictionary words, require constant spelling refinement.

On the other hand, lexicographic practice, the latest dictionaries of the modern English language, normative dictionaries, spelling dictionaries, explanatory dictionaries, explanatory dictionary, etymological dictionary, dictionaries of the correctness of English speech, dictionaries of stress and pronunciation, orthoepic dictionaries.

The basis of the literary English language is the concept of a norm, which is not constant, frozen, but changes over time. Possession of literary norms is a mandatory requirement for any educated person. Norms are fixed in dictionaries. That is why well-compiled dictionaries of the English language are so necessary. Knowledge of dictionaries and reference books, the culture of using them is an integral part of the training of bachelors, masters and specialists in all areas; but this applies especially to philologists and representatives of other humanitarian professions.

The majority of reference dictionaries (orthoepic, spelling), the bulk of explanatory dictionaries are normative. Non-normative ones include historical, etymological, etc. dictionaries. Explanatory dictionaries are linguistic dictionaries that explain the meanings of words and phraseological units of any language by means of this language itself.

Jeanne Dancette (1995: 19) defines the understanding for the translation as "the result of the confrontation and synthesis between the literal and contextual meaning of the statement". The Canadian specialist (1998) identifies three categories of comprehension difficulties: - Lexical difficulties; - Textual structure difficulties; - Pragmatic language difficulties. 3.2. Linguistic difficulties We will analyse the main linguistic nature of translation difficulties encountered, which are divided into: - terminological difficulties - Semantic difficulties. Terminological difficulties: Example Eng.: "As a rule, specialised translators can charge higher rates than generalist translators and 'localisers' or 'media translators' earn more than translators." Ro.: "Ca regulă generală, traducătorii specializați pot avea onorarii mai mari decât traducătorii generalști, iar 'localizatorii' sau 'traducătorii media' câștigă mai mult decât simplii traducători." The main objective of this section is to highlight the challenges we face when we started the research for the terminology of the

field of translation studies. To solve the difficulty mentioned in the example above, we used as translation process the loan, translating the 'localisers' with the word 'localizatorii' like that, our term is well understood in the target language, and we do not change the initial meaning of the source text.²

In conclusion, the overview of translational difficulties encountered during the writing thesis, allowed to get aware of better understanding of text, specific the lexical, grammatical, spelling difficulties.

Used Literature:

1. Narcisa Schwarz, Laura-Rebeca Stiegelbauer, Diana-Bianca Husar - Translation problems and difficulties in applied
2. NORD, Christiane, Text Analysis in Translation. Theory, Methodology and Didactic Applications of a Model of Translation-Oriented Text Analysis. Amsterdam - Atlanta: Rodopi, 1991, p.250.
3. A.Bлагова " Новейшие нормативные словари русского языка"

² Narcisa Schwarz, Laura-Rebeca Stiegelbauer, Diana-Bianca Husar - Translation problems and difficulties in applied

